

Between Complexity and Resistance: Religious Institutions and the Challenge of Terrorism and Banditry in Kontagora Emirate, Niger State

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Abstract

Terrorism and Banditry activities have affected all aspects of human life in Nigeria, particularly Kontagora Emirate, Niger State, the focus of this work. The study examines the intricate dynamics of how Islamic and Christian institutions respond to the twin challenges of banditry and religious extremism, analyzing both the factors that breed ideological complexity and the mechanism of grassroots resistance. Adopting historical methodology, the study utilized both primary and secondary sources. The study concludes that sustainable peace and counter-radicalization in the Kontagora Emirate require a bottom-up approach that empower local religious leaders, address socio-economic grievances, and integrates Faith-Based Organisation (FBO) into regional security frameworks. The Findings reveal that while certain extremist factions exploit religious rhetoric to legitimize violence, mainstream

Religious institutions serve as vital hubs for community resilience, providing humanitarian support, mediating local disputes, and fostering interfaith dialogue

Keywords: Gender Equality, Banditry, Kidnapping, Terrorism, Kontagora Emirate, WOWICAN, FOMWAN, IOC

Introduction

The increasing wave of terrorism and banditry in Northern Nigeria has become one of the most pressing security challenges confronting the nation in recent decades (Usman, 2025). These violent activities have not only threatened human lives and property but have also weakened social cohesion, disrupted economic activities, and undermined confidence in state institutions. In many communities, especially within the North-West and North Central regions, insecurity has created a climate of fear, displacement, and instability (Zakariya, 2023). Among the affected is Kontagora Emirate, a historical significant emirate in Niger State that has increasingly experienced the devastating impact of armed banditry, kidnapping, and terrorist-related violence (Zakariya, 2023).

The complexity of insecurity in Kontagora Emirate is rooted in several interrelated factors such as poverty, unemployment, weak governance, porous forest, ethnic tensions, proliferation of arms, and the declining trust between citizens and security agencies. The conditions have created an enabling environment for criminal networks and violent groups to operate with relative ease. The activities of these groups have affected rural and urban communities alike, resulting in loss of lives, destruction of livelihoods, school closures, and displacement of residents (Usman, 2025). Consequently, insecurity has evolved beyond a mere criminal issue into a broader social, political, and religious concern.

Within this context, religious institutions have emerged as important actors in the struggle against terrorism and banditry. Religious Organisation, including mosques, Islamic schools, churches, and faith-based association, play significant roles in shaping moral values, promoting peace, and fostering community resilience. In Kontagora Emirate, religious leaders often command deep respect and influence among the population, making them strategic stakeholders in efforts aimed at conflict prevention, peace building and social orientation. Through sermons, counseling, mediation, and humanitarian support, these institutions contribute to the resistance against violence and resistance. Though, religion can act as a profound force for reconciliation or a dangerous catalyst for violence.

By focusing on the experiences of the Kontagora Emirate, this research contributes to existing scholarship on religion and security in Nigeria. It highlights the importance of religious actors in confronting contemporary security threats and emphasizes the need for collaborative approaches involving government agencies, traditional authorities, and religious organisations in restoring peace and stability. Ultimately, the study aims to provide a deeper understanding of how religious

institutions navigate the tension between complexity and resistance in the face of terrorism and banditry in Kontagora Emirate, Niger State (Usman, 2023).

Literature Review

Using Frustration and Aggressive theory, developed by John Dollard and his colleagues in 1939, they explain that aggression or violence can occur when a person is prevented from achieving a goal or satisfying a need, this happened when a person faces obstacles, disappointment, or failure in trying to achieve something important for example, employment, poverty, lack of opportunity, denial of right, this can lead to fighting, rioting, destruction of property, violent protest, kidnaping, banditry, and terrorism.

The argument of Yusuf, these sects of people claim oppression as a reason for taking up arms to collect what they want from oppressors. However, many scholars have argued that there is more civilized way of demanding one's rights rather than taking up arms and also killing innocent people. For example, the wanton killing of people by Boko Haram terrorists is *repugnant to Islamic Jurisprudence in Surah Al-maaida 5:32* underpinned below with transliteration and translation (Yusuf, 2012).

Al - Maaida 5:32 Transliteration

Aw fasadin fee alardi fakaannama batala alnnasa jameeAAan waman ahyaha takaannama ahya alnnasa jameeAAan walaqad jaa thum rusuluna bialbayyinati thumma inna katheeran minhumbaAAda thalika fee alardi lamusrifoona.

Al - Maaida 5:32 Translation

Thus, we said unto the Children of Israel, that whosoever kills a human being without cause, save only in retaliation for murder or corruption in the land, it is as though they have killed all of humanity. And although our messengers brought them manifest evidence, many of them went on to commit transgressions in the land afterwards. The work is relevant to this study because terrorism a threat to the security of the people of the Kontagora was discussed in the work (Yusuf, 2012).

Saheed (2019) argued that Boko Haram, as it is popularly known, though the Islamic group refers to itself as Jama'atul Ahlis Sunnah hidda Await Waljihad (Literally translated as 'Movement for call

and striving in the way of God') or simply Yusufiya (referring to the group named after the name of its leaders, Muhammed Yusuf). On the other hand, it has been labeled as an Islamic terrorist group comprising uneducated, impoverished, and anti-status quo elements whose stock-in-trade is to detonate bombs in public buildings and shoot security personnel and others. Also, the terrorist sects are seen as revolutionaries opposed to the injustice in Nigeria and whose objective is to replace the existing decay with an Islamic order

According to Dean (2011), before Muhammad Yusuf reoriented the group as Boko Haram in the late 1990s, the sect derived its origins from the Sahaba group. Yusuf was a student of the renowned Nigerian Islamic scholar Sheikh Jafar Muhmud Adam. According to reports, the two split up in 2004 due to Yusuf's radical affiliation with Book Haram, which at the time was referred to by some as the Yusufiyya sect and had moved from Kano State to Borno State's Maduguri, Yusuf's hometown. This is relevant to this study because it gives us insight to the origin and transformation of Boko Haram and its roots.

Heinsohn (2019) identify the high birth rate in northern Nigeria, closely associated with the polygamous values prevalent in Islamic culture, combined with the neglect of these children who are left to fend for themselves on the streets, creates a vulnerable population from which terrorist and bandits recruit their members. These individuals perpetuate political violence, fueled by a distorted interpretation of the Holy Book (Qur'an).

Though he concluded by saying Islam as a religion is in itself not violence and that true Muslims do not engage in any form of violent in the name of Allah, and that Islam is interpreted to mean peace, unlike what the terrorist group hiding under Islam makes us believe. The work is relevant because it points to the fact that poverty can lead to uprising when the less privileged identity that they have been suppressed by the government, they easily seek protection from terrorist who promised heaven and earth by also brainwash the youth who are jobless.

Goshit (2005) examined the rationale behind the establishment of private security guards, He argued that the law enforcement agencies saddled with the responsibility of managing law and order have been accused of not providing adequate security to the public; rather, they are busy with ego and superiority. What this means is that there is no synergy among the security agencies to tackle crime such as terrorism and banditry, and this has made the criminals operate freely without much check.

This scenario also rears its ugly head in Kontagora emirate; therefore, the work is relevant to the study at hand

Phenson (2014) emphasized that although the role of contemporary technological devices is lacking, the worst thing is the absence of government provision, such as office and residential barracks housing for staff. As a result, some of these agencies are forced to rely on support from affluent politicians who then use them for public use. The work is relevant because security agencies designed to protect the public have now become tools in the hands of a few politicians, therefore, **abandoning** their primary assignment of public protection, as is the case of Kontagora Emirate

Audu (2021) concluded that to manage the issues of insecurity, government apparatus, both coercive and non-coercive, must work together to achieve national unity, and the government also needs to address and tackle the issues of poverty, hunger, quality education, population growth, underdevelopment, and corruption in the private and public institutions. The opinion of the author has provided a basis for understanding the framework of this work. Thus, threats to life and property, whether from armed robbers, Boko Haram, or bandits jeopardizing citizens' freedom, were indicative of a deficiency in internal security, which serves as the foundation for this study

Dan Fulani (2004) argued that national leaders should seek the security of their nation beyond militarism, mobilization instead, all national resources and sectors, including the legal, economic, socio-political, environmental, and psychological. To him, when the welfare of the citizens is taken care of adequately by the leaders, there will be less threat to life and property, thus, the work is relevant to this study.

Conceptual Clarifications

Banditry

Gillian (2018), the term "banditry" describes organised crime that involves coercion and violence, such as kidnapping, extortion, and robbery. It is also viewed as criminal organizations engaged in such operations to make cash, resulting in major social and economic implications.

Terrorism

Ibrahim, et al. (2016). Terrorism is defined as the intentional use of violence to instill widespread fear in a society to further specific political aims. It is also the premeditated use of violence or threats against innocent persons to intimidate others into taking actions they would not otherwise take.

Kidnapping

Ibrahim, B, & Jamil, I. (2019). Kidnapping is a criminal offense in which perpetrators abduct, transport, and confine their victims.

Armed Robbery

Kamar et al. (2022). Armed robbery, on the other hand, is a criminal act that involves a serious threat to national security, and it attracts capital punishment, in justice systems of most countries of the world.

Kontagora Emirate

Geographically, Kontagora is a significant town located on the southern bank of the Kontagora River in northwestern Niger State, Nigeria. Kontagora emirate comprises of the chiefdom of Kontagora, Wushishi, Magama, Mariga, Mashegu, and Rijau. It is the home of many prominent Nigerians. The majority of the numerous indigenous tribes of the Emirate include the Kambari, Nupe, Gbagyi, Kamuku, Gungawa, Hun-saare, Hausa, Busa, and Koro.

Land and People of Kontagora Emirate

Geographically, Kontagora Emirate is located in the mid-western part of Niger State. It shared borders in the west with Borgu, narrow strip of Nupe land separated it from the railway as far as Zungeru on its South Eastern border to the North East. It is separated from Bida by River Kaduna and bordered in the North by Yauri (in Kebbi State). The Emirate consists of the chiefdoms of Wushishi, Sarkin-Bauchi and Kagara, all administratively grouped into Kontagora, Mariga, Magama, and Rafi local government area with a population of 260,700 and coverings 1,826km (Adamu, 2015). It is home of many prominent Nigerian ethnicities. The Nupe, Gbagyi, Kamuku, Gungawa, Hun-saare, Hausa, Busa and Koro form the majority of numerous indigenous ethnic groups of the Emirate: others like the Yoruba, Igbo also live peacefully with the indigenes (Adamu, 2015).

Kontagora Emirate encompasses a number of towns and villages, primarily located in Kontagora Local Government Area (LGA) in Niger State. The emirate covers a vast area and includes both

urban and rural settlements, playing a key role in the socio-economic activities of its people. Major Towns includes; Kontagora, Masuga, Kotonkoro, Magama, and villages, which include but not limited to Gulbin Boka, Sabon Gari, Dukku, Gusamin Gwari, Tungan Gari, Zango, Rijau.

The Role of Religious Institutions in Mitigating Terrorism, and Banditry in Kontagora Emirate

Terrorism and banditry have posed significant security challenges in many parts of northern Nigeria, particularly in the Kontagora Emirate of Niger State. The prevalence of these acts has disrupted socioeconomic activities, displaced communities, and instilled fear in the local population. With the rise of these violent activities, organizations and religious bodies have increasingly become pivotal in addressing the crisis, advocating for peace, and providing support to victims. The collaboration between civil society organizations (CSOs), non-governmental organizations (NGOs), religious leaders, and government agencies has emerged as a crucial mechanism for combating terrorism and banditry in the region (Zakari, 2023).

Religious bodies, particularly those associated with Islam and Christianity, have played a critical role in countering the narratives that drive terrorism and banditry. Religious leaders often serve as moral authorities within their communities, preaching peace and the rejection of violence as a means to resolve grievances. Many religious bodies have also been at the forefront of peace-building initiatives, working towards reconciliation between conflicting parties, providing humanitarian assistance, and promoting dialogue among different groups (Usman, 2023).

The Impacts of Islam

1. Misuse of Islamic Teachings by Extremist Groups

Extremist groups often exploit religious rhetoric, distorting Islamic teachings to justify their violent actions. These groups misinterpret concepts such as *jihad* to legitimize acts of terrorism and banditry, which are primarily economically or politically motivated. The manipulation of Islamic ideologies, especially among vulnerable populations with limited religious knowledge, exacerbates the issue (Adesoji, 2011).

2. Islamic Leadership's Role in Countering Terrorism and Banditry

Islamic scholars and leaders in the Kontagora Emirate have been at the forefront of condemning terrorism and banditry. They emphasize that Islam promotes peace and condemns violence, directly

opposing the extremist narrative. For instance, the issuance of *fatwas* by prominent clerics declaring terrorism and banditry as un-Islamic has been an effective tool in delegitimizing extremist ideologies (Suleiman, M., & Ismail, N. 2018).

3. Islamic Teachings and Community Resilience

Islamic teachings on charity and social welfare have been mobilized to support victims of violence in Kontagora Emirate. Through *zakat* and *sadaqah*, Islamic organizations provide essential services to those affected by terrorism and banditry, helping to alleviate the economic pressures that fuel such activities (Ahmed, 2020). These charitable actions reinforce the values of community solidarity and mutual aid, which are essential in building resilience against the destabilizing effects of violence.

4. Rehabilitation and Reintegration Efforts

Some Islamic-based rehabilitation programs have been developed to help former extremists and bandits reintegrate into society. These programs focus on religious reeducation, counseling, and skill acquisition, offering alternatives to violence. This aligns with Islamic principles of mercy and forgiveness, which encourage individuals to seek repentance and reintegrate into society (Mustapha, 2022).

The Impacts of Christianity

Christianity has had a profound impact on efforts to address terrorism and banditry in the Kontagora Emirate. Christian leaders have consistently advocated for non-violence and have used biblical teachings to promote peace and forgiveness, even in the face of violence. Churches have become safe havens for displaced persons, offering shelter, food, and medical care. Moreover, Christian organizations have been instrumental in fostering dialogue between conflicting communities and working alongside other religious bodies to resolve disputes and rebuild trust (Yahaya, 2020).

Their interventions have had several notable impacts below:

1. Promotion of Peace and Reconciliation

Christian leaders in the Kontagora Emirate have consistently preached peace and forgiveness, drawing on biblical teachings to encourage non-violence and reconciliation. Churches and Christian organizations often organize interfaith dialogues and peace workshops aimed at reducing tensions

between conflicting communities and fostering mutual understanding. These initiatives have helped to calm tensions and prevent further escalation of violence (Bawa, 2022).

2. Humanitarian Support

Many Christian organizations have been involved in providing humanitarian aid to communities affected by terrorism and banditry. This includes offering food, shelter, and medical assistance to internally displaced persons (IDPs) who have been forced to flee their homes due to insecurity. Through charitable efforts, Christian groups have provided relief to victims of violence, which has contributed to the resilience of local communities and reinforced social cohesion (Yohanna, 2021).

3. Advocacy for Social Justice and Security Reforms

Christian organizations have been vocal in advocating for justice and the protection of human rights in the face of terrorism and banditry. They have called on government authorities to improve security measures, enhance social justice, and address the underlying causes of violence, such as poverty and marginalization. Their advocacy has often prompted the government to take more decisive actions in combating terrorism in the emirate (Usman, 2025).

4. Psychosocial Support and Trauma Healing

The psychological impact of terrorism and banditry on communities in Kontagora has been profound. Churches have provided psychosocial support, counseling, and trauma healing programs to help individuals and families cope with the emotional and mental effects of violence. This has been vital in restoring hope and rebuilding the lives of those affected by these crises (Olu, 2022).

The involvement of Christianity in addressing terrorism and banditry in Kontagora Emirate has been instrumental in promoting peace, providing humanitarian aid, advocating for security reforms, and offering psychosocial support. These efforts have contributed to stabilizing communities and mitigating the effects of insecurity in the region.

Conclusion

This study has looked into the role of religious bodies on terrorism and banditry in Kontagora, particularly Christianity and Islam. The findings reveal that religious institutions play a significant role in promoting peace, moral, discipline, and social cohesion within the Emirate. Through sermons, public enlightenment campaigns, interfaith dialogue, and community engagement, religious leaders

have contributed to discouraging violent extremism and criminal activities. Their teachings often emphasize tolerance, justice, and the sanctity of human life, thereby countering ideologies that fuel terrorism and banditry.

In conclusion, religious bodies in Kontagora Emirate remain indispensable actors in the fight against terrorism and banditry. With improved collaboration and support, their influence can be further harnessed to promote lasting peace, security, and sustainable development in the Emirate,

However, despite these efforts, challenges such as limited resources, inadequate coordination, and the manipulation of religion by extremist elements continue to undermine progress.

Recommendations

The study recommends that, there is need for sustained partnership between religious institutions, security agencies, and government authorities to enhance peace-building initiatives in Kontagora Emirate. Strengthening religious education, promoting interfaith harmony, and empowering youth through faith-based programs remain crucial strategies for curbing terrorism and banditry.

There is also a need for religious leaders and organisations to explore and examine the level of insecurity and violence in Kontagora Emirate, through the teachings of the Holy Books and use their influence to teach, educate, mobilise, their congregation and challenge, harmful interpretations of religious texts that justify violence, as well as condemn all forms of violence, security threat posed by domestic and physical violence, gender inequality and all other forms of sufferings in Kontagora Emirate.

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